

Foreword

It is with great pride and a deep sense of responsibility that I introduce this groundbreaking report on the potential integration of Artificial Intelligence into NRC Ukraine's operations. Over the past years, our team has worked tirelessly to provide critical aid and support to those affected by the ongoing conflict.

However, the complexity and scale of the challenges we face demand new approaches, new tools, and new ways of thinking. The work presented here by Thomas Byrnes offers a comprehensive analysis of how emerging AI technologies—particularly Natural Language Processing and Generative AI—can help us enhance our efficiency, responsiveness, and impact.

In a rapidly evolving humanitarian landscape, the integration of AI offers immense potential. It is not just about improving our internal processes or strengthening decision-making. It is about finding new ways to serve the people who depend on us, making our interventions more timely, more targeted, and ultimately more effective. This report provides a roadmap for responsible AI adoption, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations, transparency, and safeguarding the rights and dignity of the vulnerable populations we serve.

With NRC Ukraine's commitment to innovation, we now take a significant step forward by publishing this report as a Digital Public Good, ensuring that its insights and recommendations are accessible to the wider humanitarian community. This is not just a technical document—it is a vision for the future of humanitarian work, one where AI plays a central role in making us more effective in serving those in need.

We hope that this work inspires collaboration and shared learning, guiding humanitarian organizations and partners in responsibly harnessing AI for the greater good.

Roberto Vila-Sexto
Country Director, NRC Ukraine

Executive Summary

This report, authored by Thomas Byrnes, Digital Humanitarian Consultant at MarketImpact, offers a detailed exploration of how Artificial Intelligence (AI)—particularly Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Generative AI technologies—can be integrated into the operations of the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) Ukraine. The analysis focuses on leveraging AI to enhance operational efficiency, improve decision-making, and increase overall impact across key areas of NRC's humanitarian work. Additionally, the report addresses the ethical, operational, and strategic considerations critical to ensuring the responsible and effective adoption of AI within the humanitarian sector.

Objectives and Scope

The report assesses the potential benefits and risks of integrating AI into NRC Ukraine's humanitarian efforts, aiming to:

- Improve **strategic planning** and decision-making.
- Enhance **advocacy** and communications.
- Strengthen **safety and security** measures.
- Streamline **human resources** management and capacity building.
- Optimize **monitoring, evaluation, and learning** processes.
- Facilitate **proposal development and reporting**.
- Enhance **technical program design and implementation**.

Methodology

The analysis is based on:

- **Literature Review:** Examining current AI technologies and trends in humanitarian contexts.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Interviews with NRC Ukraine staff, partners, experts, and government representatives to gather insights on needs, challenges, and perspectives regarding AI adoption.
- **Program Analysis:** Reviewing NRC Ukraine's strategies and operations to identify AI use cases aligned with strategic objectives and humanitarian values.

AI Technology Landscape

- **Overview of NLP and Generative AI:** Highlighting their capabilities in content creation, data analysis, and language processing.
- **Current Applications:** AI is used in information dissemination, language services, data analysis, and feedback mechanisms within the humanitarian sector.
- **Future Directions:** Emphasizing the development of robust, adaptable, and culturally sensitive AI models, integrating AI with decision support tools, and embedding ethical safeguards.

Potential AI Use Cases

The report identifies two categories of AI use cases:

1. **Direct Prompting Use Cases:** Immediate access to AI capabilities through natural language prompts without coding or technical integration.

2. **Integrated or Customized Use Cases:** Tailoring AI models to meet specific organizational needs through coding and technical integration.

Applications across Operational Areas:

- **Senior Management:** Strategic planning, decision support, communication enhancement.
- **Advocacy and Communications:** Content generation, multilingual translation, personalized content delivery.
- **Safety and Security:** Real-time information gathering, risk assessment, predictive risk modeling.
- **Human Resources and Capacity Building:** Talent management, staff development, automated onboarding.
- **Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning:** Automated data analysis, predictive analytics, anomaly detection.
- **Proposal Development and Reporting:** Drafting proposal sections, compliance checking, content management integration.
- **Technical Program Design and Implementation:** Needs assessment tools, resource allocation optimization, predictive analytics.

Recommendations for Customized Use Cases:

- **Senior Management:** Implement an AI-powered analytics dashboard that aggregates data from various programs to visualize performance metrics and identify areas needing attention, enhancing strategic decision-making.
- **Advocacy and Communications:** Develop an AI-driven content management system that automates tagging, categorization, and distribution of communication materials across multiple platforms and languages.
- **Safety and Security:** Create an automated threat detection system that analyzes data from various sources to identify potential security risks and provide real-time alerts to HSS teams.
- **Human Resources and Capacity Building:** Implement an AI-powered skills assessment and matching system to analyze employee profiles and match staff with suitable positions and training opportunities.
- **Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning:** Develop an automated data analysis tool that processes large volumes of structured and unstructured data to identify trends, patterns, and anomalies in program performance.
- **Proposal Development and Reporting:** Create an AI-powered compliance checking system that automatically reviews proposals and reports for adherence to donor requirements and organizational standards.
- **Technical Program Design and Implementation:** Prioritize the development of an AI-Powered Cash Assistance Decision Support tool to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of aid modality selection, ensuring more targeted and impactful interventions.

These recommendations focus on leveraging AI technologies to address specific operational challenges and improve efficiency across various departments within NRC Ukraine. Implementation should be approached cautiously, with careful consideration given to data protection, ethical use, and the need for human oversight.

Cross-Cutting Risks

The report highlights several risks associated with AI adoption:

- **Data Privacy and Protection:** Risk of data breaches or misuse of sensitive beneficiary information.
- **Algorithmic Bias and Ethical Implications:** Potential for AI models to perpetuate biases, leading to unintended discrimination.
- **Overreliance on AI and Erosion of Human Expertise:** Risk of devaluing human expertise and contextual understanding.
- **Lack of Transparency and Accountability:** Challenges in interpreting complex AI models, undermining trust.
- **Security Vulnerabilities and Misuse Potential:** Risks of cyber-attacks and misuse of AI tools by malicious actors.
- **Operational and Environmental Challenges:** Infrastructure limitations and security risks in conflict zones.
- **Regulatory and Legal Implications:** Need to comply with evolving data privacy and AI ethics regulations.

Implementation Considerations

Key factors for successful AI integration include:

- **Existing IT Infrastructure:** Assessing and enhancing hardware, software, and network capacities.
- **Staff Training and Capacity Building:** Enhancing AI literacy, technical proficiency, and fostering a culture of continuous learning.
- **Data Privacy and Ethical Concerns:** Implementing robust data governance frameworks, ethical guidelines, and stakeholder engagement.
- **Operational Environment Challenges:** Developing contingency plans to address infrastructure and connectivity issues in conflict zones.
- **Feasibility Assessment:** Evaluating organizational readiness, resource availability, and specific use cases.

Recommendations for Responsible AI Implementation

1. **Prioritize Practical AI Tools:** Identify and implement AI tools offering immediate efficiency gains within existing workflows.
2. **Automate Basic Processes:** Streamline repetitive tasks through automation to save time and resources.
3. **Establish Ethical Guidelines and Governance Structures:** Develop comprehensive principles to ensure ethical and responsible AI use, emphasizing transparency and accountability.

4. **Prioritize Rights-Based Approaches and Algorithmic Accountability:** Ensure AI systems respect and uphold the rights of affected communities, promoting fairness and inclusivity.
5. **Foster Organizational Intelligence and Capacity Building:** Invest in staff training, enhance data literacy, and promote a data-driven culture.
6. **Adopt an Incremental Implementation Approach:** Start with low-risk applications and expand as capacity and readiness grow.
7. **Engage Stakeholders and Foster Collaboration:** Involve beneficiaries, partners, and stakeholders in AI initiatives to maximize benefits and ensure cultural sensitivity.
8. **Establish Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms:** Implement systems to assess the impact of AI initiatives and inform ongoing strategy.

Conclusion

The integration of AI technologies presents significant opportunities for NRC Ukraine to enhance its humanitarian operations, improve efficiency, and better serve crisis-affected communities. However, this requires careful navigation of ethical, operational, and strategic challenges. By adopting a responsible and incremental approach, investing in capacity building, and prioritizing ethical considerations, NRC Ukraine can harness the transformative potential of AI while upholding its humanitarian principles and values.

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	8
AI Technology Landscape.....	8
Potential AI Use Case for NRC Ukraine.....	10
Potential AI Use Cases for Senior Management in NRC.....	11
Potential AI Use Cases for Advocacy and Communications.....	13
Potential AI Use Cases for Safety and Security.....	16
Potential AI Use Cases for Human Resources and Capacity Building.....	17
Potential AI Use Cases for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning.....	19
Potential AI Use Cases for Proposal Development and Reporting.....	21
Potential AI Use Cases for Technical Program Design and Implementation.....	23
Cross-Cutting Risks with AI NLP for NRC Ukraine.....	25
Implementation Considerations.....	28
Recommendations for Responsible AI Implementation at NRC Ukraine.....	31
Conclusion.....	33
Bibliography.....	34

<i>Table of Abbreviations:</i>	
AI	- Artificial Intelligence
NLP	- Natural Language Processing
RPA	- Robotic Process Automation
LLMs	- Large Language Models
NRC	- Norwegian Refugee Council
MPCA	- Multipurpose Cash Assistance
NEED-Cash	- NRC's digital platform for cash assistance self-registration
IT	- Information Technology
HR	- Human Resources
M&E	- Monitoring and Evaluation

Introduction

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), especially in natural language processing (NLP) and generative AI technologies, presents significant opportunities and challenges for humanitarian organizations like the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) Ukraine. This report explores how these technologies can enhance NRC Ukraine's operations by improving efficiency and decision-making, while addressing ethical, operational, and strategic considerations for responsible AI adoption.

Objectives and Scope

This report assesses the potential benefits and risks of integrating AI—specifically NLP and generative AI—into NRC Ukraine's humanitarian efforts. It focuses on enhancing accountability, effectiveness, efficiency, and impact across various operational areas, including:

- Strategic planning
- Advocacy
- Safety and security
- Human resources
- Monitoring and evaluation
- Proposal development
- Technical program implementation

The report identifies how AI can streamline processes, automate tasks, and extract valuable insights from data to improve humanitarian interventions. It also examines critical implementation factors such as IT infrastructure, staff training, data privacy, operational challenges in conflict zones, and change management. Actionable recommendations are provided to foster a culture of learning and adaptation while aligning with NRC's humanitarian mission and principles.

Methodology

To achieve these objectives, the report utilized:

- **Literature Review:** Examined the status, applications, and trends of AI technologies across sectors, focusing on their potential in humanitarian contexts. Sources included academic papers, industry reports, and authoritative publications.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Conducted interviews in November 2023 with NRC Ukraine staff, partners, experts, and government representatives to gather insights on needs, challenges, and perspectives regarding AI adoption, emphasizing humanitarian principles.
- **Program Analysis:** Analyzed NRC Ukraine's program strategy and operations to identify potential AI use cases aligned with strategic objectives and humanitarian values.

By integrating diverse perspectives and data sources, the report provides a comprehensive analysis of opportunities for leveraging AI technologies responsibly.

AI Technology Landscape

Overview of NLP and Generative AI

Generative AI utilizes algorithms that learn from vast datasets to create new, original content such as text, images, or videos in response to prompts. Unlike traditional AI models that rely

on replication, generative AI mimics the structure of the original data without duplicating it. Prominent examples of this technology include OpenAI's GPT-4, Google's LaMDA, and Anthropic's Claude, all of which exhibit advanced language comprehension and generation capabilities.

These advancements are largely driven by foundation models, which can process unstructured data without needing pre-labeled training datasets. These models are highly versatile, performing multiple tasks and generating content on demand. Their ability to reduce workloads—often by at least 20%—makes them particularly transformative in humanitarian functions, from document creation to data analysis.

Current Applications

In the humanitarian sector, Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies are already widely deployed, playing a critical role in the following areas:

- **Information Dissemination:** Chatbots and virtual assistants provide crucial support to vulnerable populations, such as refugees, offering timely information about aid services.
- **Language Services:** Machine translation tools help bridge language barriers, ensuring accessible communication. Organizations like *Translators without Borders* facilitate understanding across diverse languages, making essential information available to those who need it.
- **Data Analysis:** NLP tools are used to sift through unstructured data—such as field reports, social media updates, and news articles—to extract actionable insights. The *World Health Organization (WHO)* and *International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC)* utilize these tools to monitor misinformation and assess community needs.
- **Feedback and Adaptation:** NLP allows for the analysis of beneficiary feedback to adjust and refine programs. For example, the *International Rescue Committee* uses these insights to ensure its programs are responsive to community needs.

Furthermore, participatory approaches involving affected communities in AI model development ensure that the technology remains culturally sensitive and aligned with the ethical principles of humanitarian work. This promotes responsible AI usage, minimizing the risk of misuse or bias.

Future Directions

The future of AI in the humanitarian sector points towards developing more robust, adaptable, and culturally sensitive models. Research focuses on enhancing the flexibility and resilience of AI systems, ensuring that they can be used effectively in dynamic and challenging environments. Another priority is the integration of AI with recommender systems and decision support tools, which would allow humanitarian organizations to optimize their operations further, from resource allocation to beneficiary engagement.

Central to this development is the commitment to responsible AI practices, prioritizing the needs and rights of affected communities. As AI continues to evolve, embedding ethical safeguards and ensuring transparency in AI systems will be critical to maintaining trust and credibility in humanitarian applications.

Potential AI Use Case for NRC Ukraine

As AI technologies like NLP and generative AI become increasingly sophisticated, their potential applications within humanitarian organizations grow more varied and impactful. AI tools can streamline operations, improve decision-making, and enhance responsiveness to beneficiary needs. However, understanding how to integrate these technologies effectively requires distinguishing between two main categories of AI use cases: **Direct Prompting** and **Integrated or Customized Use Cases**. These categories distinguish the level of complexity, technical integration, and customization required when leveraging AI tools in operational settings.

Direct Prompting Use Cases

Direct prompting involves interacting with AI models through natural language prompts without the need for coding or technical integration. This category allows users to access AI capabilities immediately, providing quick solutions to everyday tasks.

Characteristics:

- No coding or technical setup is required.
- Immediate access to AI tools.
- Ideal for tasks such as content creation, brainstorming, answering questions, or summarizing information.

Examples:

- An employee uses an AI tool like ChatGPT to draft a report or document.
- A customer support agent queries an AI model to find solutions to frequently asked questions.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases

This category involves tailoring AI models to meet specific organizational needs through coding and technical integration. These use cases often connect AI tools to proprietary data, workflows, or systems, allowing for advanced automation and deeper insights.

Characteristics:

- Requires technical integration and, in some cases, coding.
- AI models are customized to specific tasks and connected to internal data or processes.
- Suitable for building AI agents that automate complex tasks or for integrating AI into existing software systems.

Examples:

- Developing a custom chatbot that accesses internal knowledge bases to provide tailored responses.
- Integrating AI into a CRM system to analyze interactions and improve customer engagement.
- Creating an AI tool that automates data entry from documents, reducing manual workloads.

By clearly defining these categories, organizations like NRC can identify which solutions provide immediate benefits and which require more technical integration for deeper

organizational impact. Below, we explore these two categories of AI use cases and how they can be applied to enhance NRC's humanitarian efforts.

Potential AI Use Cases for Senior Management in NRC

As the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) continues to navigate complex humanitarian landscapes, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies presents a significant opportunity to enhance strategic decision-making, operational efficiency, and overall impact. For senior management, understanding how AI can be leveraged is crucial for steering the organization towards greater effectiveness while upholding humanitarian principles.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Senior Management in NRC

Description: Direct Prompting Use Cases involve interacting with AI models—such as ChatGPT, Claude, or Bing—directly through natural language prompts. These applications require no coding or technical integration, providing immediate access to AI capabilities out-of-the-box.

Characteristics:

- **Ease of Use:** No technical expertise or software development is needed; users interact with AI using everyday language.
- **Immediate Deployment:** Tools are readily available and can be used without delay.
- **Versatility:** Suitable for a wide range of tasks, including drafting documents, brainstorming ideas, summarizing reports, and answering queries.

Potential Applications for Senior Management:

- **Strategic Planning and Document Drafting:**
 - AI can assist in creating initial drafts of strategic documents, policy briefs, and board reports, saving time and ensuring clarity.
 - *Example:* A senior manager uses ChatGPT to generate a first draft of the annual operational plan, which can then be refined and customized.
- **Information Synthesis and Summarization:**
 - AI models can quickly summarize lengthy reports, research papers, and meeting notes, allowing managers to grasp essential information efficiently.
 - *Example:* Summarizing a 50-page field assessment report into key findings and recommendations.
- **Brainstorming and Ideation:**
 - AI can generate ideas for program development, fundraising strategies, or stakeholder engagement initiatives.
 - *Example:* Generating a list of innovative approaches to enhance donor engagement based on current trends.
- **Decision Support:**
 - Providing quick answers to complex questions by analyzing vast amounts of publicly available data.
 - *Example:* Asking an AI model about best practices in emergency shelter provision in similar contexts.
- **Communication Enhancement:**
 - Crafting emails, speeches, and presentations with appropriate tone and messaging tailored to diverse audiences.

- *Example:* Drafting a compelling speech for a fundraising event that resonates with potential donors.

Benefits:

- **Time Efficiency:** Reduces the time spent on drafting and reviewing documents.
- **Improved Quality:** Enhances the clarity and professionalism of communications.
- **Accessibility:** Requires minimal training, making it accessible to all staff members.

Considerations:

- **Data Privacy:** Avoid inputting sensitive or confidential information into AI tools that process data externally.
- **Accuracy Verification:** AI-generated content should be reviewed for factual accuracy and alignment with NRC's policies.
- **Ethical Use:** Maintain ethical standards by ensuring content is appropriate and culturally sensitive.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Senior Management in NRC

Potential Applications for Senior Management:**• Advanced Decision Support Systems:**

- Developing AI-powered analytics platforms that provide real-time insights from internal data, aiding strategic decision-making.
- *Example:* An AI dashboard that aggregates data from various programs to visualize performance metrics and identify areas needing attention.

• Predictive Analytics for Crisis Response:

- Utilizing AI models to predict humanitarian needs, population movements, or potential crises based on historical and real-time data.
- *Example:* An AI system forecasts an influx of displaced persons due to emerging conflict, allowing proactive resource allocation.

• Risk Management and Compliance Monitoring:

- Automating the monitoring of compliance with donor requirements, legal regulations, and internal policies.
- *Example:* An AI tool scans project documentation to ensure compliance with donor stipulations before submission.

• Customized Knowledge Management Systems:

- Implementing AI to organize and retrieve information from internal databases, reports, and documents.
- *Example:* An AI assistant that helps staff quickly find policies, guidelines, or past project reports relevant to their needs.

• Enhanced Donor Relationship Management:

- Integrating AI into CRM systems to analyze donor interactions, preferences, and giving patterns to improve engagement strategies.
- *Example:* AI identifies donors who are likely to increase their contributions and suggests personalized communication approaches.

• Automated Financial Analysis:

- AI systems can analyze financial data to detect anomalies, optimize budgeting, and improve financial planning.
- *Example:* An AI tool monitors expenditure patterns across projects to identify potential overspending or savings opportunities.

Benefits:

- **Strategic Insights:** Provides deeper understanding through data analysis, supporting informed decision-making.
- **Operational Efficiency:** Automates complex and time-consuming tasks, reducing errors and freeing up staff capacity.
- **Competitive Advantage:** Tailored AI solutions can enhance NRC's ability to respond effectively in dynamic environments.

Considerations:

- **Resource Investment:** Requires investment in technology, development, and skilled personnel.
- **Data Security and Privacy:** Must implement robust cybersecurity measures to protect sensitive organizational and beneficiary data.
- **Change Management:** Successful adoption depends on effective staff training and managing the cultural shift within the organization.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensure that AI implementations comply with local and international laws, including data protection regulations.

Potential AI Use Cases for Advocacy and Communications

Effective advocacy and communications are critical for the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) to raise awareness, influence policy, and engage with stakeholders, beneficiaries, and partners. Leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies can significantly enhance these efforts by enabling the creation of tailored messaging, overcoming language barriers, and facilitating efficient content generation.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Advocacy and Communications

- **Content Generation and Drafting:**
 - AI can assist in creating first drafts of press releases, blog posts, social media content, newsletters, and other communication materials, saving time and ensuring consistency in messaging.
 - *Example:* A communications officer uses ChatGPT to generate a draft article highlighting NRC's recent humanitarian efforts, which can then be edited and personalized.
- **Multilingual Translation:**
 - AI models can provide quick translations of content into multiple languages, helping to reach diverse audiences.
 - *Example:* Translating a press release from English to Ukrainian and Russian using an AI translation tool to ensure accessibility for local stakeholders.
- **Message Tailoring:**
 - Generating tailored messages for different stakeholder groups by adjusting tone, style, and content to resonate with specific audiences.
 - *Example:* Creating separate versions of a campaign message for donors, policymakers, and beneficiaries, each crafted to appeal to their interests and concerns.
- **Idea Generation and Brainstorming:**

- AI can provide creative ideas for advocacy campaigns, slogans, or engagement strategies.
- *Example:* Generating a list of potential themes for an upcoming advocacy campaign on displacement issues.
- **Summarization of Reports and Data:**
 - Summarizing lengthy reports or data into key points that can be easily communicated to the public or stakeholders.
 - *Example:* Condensing a comprehensive needs assessment report into a one-page briefing for media outlets.

Benefits:

- Time Savings: Reduces the time required to draft and translate content.
- Enhanced Reach: Facilitates communication with multilingual audiences without delay.
- Consistency: Ensures messaging aligns with organizational tone and objectives.
- Cost-Effective: Minimizes the need for external translation services or content creation.

Considerations:

- Quality Assurance: AI-generated content should be reviewed for accuracy, cultural sensitivity, and appropriateness.
- Data Privacy: Avoid sharing sensitive information with AI tools that process data externally.
- Ethical Use: Ensure that translations and messages are accurate and do not inadvertently misinform or offend.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Advocacy and Communications

- **Automated Multilingual Communication Platforms:**
 - Integrating AI-powered translation services into NRC's communication channels (e.g., websites, mobile apps) to provide real-time multilingual support.
 - *Example:* A website that automatically displays content in the user's preferred language, with AI ensuring accurate and contextually appropriate translations.
- **Personalized Content Delivery Systems:**
 - Using AI to analyze stakeholder engagement data and deliver personalized content based on user preferences and behaviors.
 - *Example:* An AI-driven newsletter system that curates articles and updates for subscribers based on their interests and past interactions.
- **Chatbots for Stakeholder Engagement:**
 - Developing AI chatbots that can interact with website visitors, answer frequently asked questions, and provide information about NRC's work in multiple languages.
 - *Example:* A chatbot that assists donors in navigating donation options or provides beneficiaries with information on available services.
- **Sentiment Analysis and Media Monitoring:**
 - Implementing AI tools to monitor social media and news outlets for mentions of NRC, humanitarian issues, or relevant topics, analyzing sentiment to inform advocacy strategies.

- *Example:* An AI system that alerts the communications team to trending topics or public concerns, enabling timely responses.
- **Content Management and Workflow Automation:**
 - Integrating AI into content management systems to automate tagging, categorization, and distribution of communication materials.
 - *Example:* AI automatically tags new content with relevant keywords and schedules it for publication across various platforms.
- **Visual Content Generation (with Caution):**
 - Utilizing AI to create visual content such as infographics or data visualizations to support advocacy campaigns, ensuring compliance with ethical guidelines.
 - *Example:* Generating an infographic that illustrates displacement statistics, created with AI tools but reviewed by designers for accuracy and appropriateness.

Benefits:

- **Enhanced Engagement:** Tailored and timely communication can improve stakeholder engagement and advocacy impact.
- **Operational Efficiency:** Automation reduces manual workload and speeds up content delivery.
- **Data-Driven Strategies:** Insights from AI analytics inform more effective advocacy campaigns.
- **Broader Reach:** Multilingual support and personalized content expand the organization's audience.

Considerations:

- **Technical Resources:** Requires investment in technology and potentially hiring or training staff with technical expertise.
- **Data Security and Privacy:** Must ensure that integrated systems protect user data and comply with privacy regulations.
- **Ethical Guidelines:** Establish clear policies for the use of AI, especially concerning content authenticity and the use of AI-generated visuals.
- **Cultural Sensitivity:** AI tools should be configured to respect cultural nuances and avoid miscommunication.

Caution on AI-Generated Visuals:

While AI tools can generate images and visual content, NRC should exercise caution in using AI-generated visuals to depict real humanitarian crises or human rights issues. As noted by Jumbert (2024), relying on synthetic images can undermine credibility and public trust. Therefore, NRC should prioritize authentic visuals and establish guidelines for responsible use if AI-generated images are considered.¹

For NRC's Advocacy and Communications efforts, AI technologies offer substantial opportunities to enhance messaging, broaden reach, and engage effectively with diverse audiences. Direct Prompting Use Cases provide immediate benefits with minimal barriers to

¹ Jumbert, M. G. (2024). The AI Dilemma: Can Artificial Images of War and Suffering Stir Empathy? Global Policy Opinion, March 15, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.globalpolicyjournal.com/blog/15/03/2024/ai-dilemma-can-artificial-images-war-and-suffering-stir-empathy> [Accessed April 20, 2024].

entry, enabling staff to quickly generate and translate content. Integrated or Customized Use Cases allow for a deeper transformation of communication strategies through personalized engagement, automation, and advanced analytics. By thoughtfully implementing these AI applications, NRC can amplify its advocacy impact while maintaining ethical standards and respecting the cultural and linguistic diversity of its stakeholders. It is essential to balance technological innovation with human oversight to ensure that communications remain authentic, accurate, and aligned with the organization's mission and values.

Potential AI Use Cases for Safety and Security

Ensuring the safety and security of staff and operations in conflict zones and high-risk environments is a critical challenge for the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC). Leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies can significantly enhance situational awareness, risk assessment, and proactive mitigation strategies. AI use cases in this domain can be categorized into Direct Prompting Use Cases and Integrated or Customized Use Cases.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Safety and Security

- **Real-Time Information Gathering:**
 - AI models can provide summaries of recent security incidents, travel advisories, or conflict developments based on publicly available information.
 - *Example:* A security officer asks ChatGPT for a summary of the latest security incidents in a specific region to inform daily briefings.
- **Risk Assessment Support:**
 - AI can assist in identifying potential risks by analyzing text inputs describing situations or locations.
 - *Example:* Inputting details of a planned field mission to receive a risk assessment summary highlighting potential security concerns.
- **Incident Reporting Assistance:**
 - Generating initial drafts of incident reports or security briefs to streamline documentation.
 - *Example:* Using AI to draft an incident report based on bullet points provided by field staff, which can then be reviewed and finalized.
- **Policy and Protocol Clarification:**
 - Quickly retrieving information on security protocols or procedures from internal documents.
 - *Example:* Asking AI for a summary of evacuation procedures for a particular area or scenario.

Benefits:

- **Time Efficiency:** Accelerates information gathering and report drafting.
- **Improved Situational Awareness:** Provides quick access to relevant information.
- **Resource Optimization:** Allows staff to focus on critical decision-making.

Considerations:

- **Data Accuracy:** AI relies on available data, which may not always be up-to-date or specific to NRC's internal information.

- Confidentiality: Avoid sharing sensitive or classified information with external AI tools.
- Verification Needed: AI-generated insights should be cross-checked with reliable sources.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Safety and Security

- **Automated Threat Detection Systems:**
 - Implementing AI models that analyze data from various sources—such as incident reports, social media, satellite imagery—to identify potential threats and anomalies.
 - *Example:* An AI system monitors social media and news feeds for signs of escalating tensions near NRC operations, alerting staff to potential risks.
- **Predictive Risk Modeling:**
 - Using machine learning algorithms to predict security incidents based on historical data and current trends.
 - *Example:* An AI model forecasts the likelihood of security incidents in specific regions, aiding in mission planning and resource allocation.
- **Real-Time Situational Awareness Platforms:**
 - Integrating AI with geospatial data to provide real-time maps highlighting security hotspots and safe routes.
 - *Example:* A dashboard that visualizes current security risks, enabling field teams to adjust routes and plans accordingly.
- **Incident Data Analysis:**
 - Analyzing past incident reports to identify patterns and inform future security strategies.
 - *Example:* AI analyzes historical security incidents to identify common factors, informing training and prevention efforts.

Benefits:

- Enhanced Proactivity: Allows for early detection of potential threats.
- Data-Driven Decisions: Improves the quality of security planning and response.
- Resource Optimization: Allocates security resources more effectively based on risk levels.

Considerations:

- Technical Expertise: Requires investment in technology and skilled personnel.
- Data Privacy and Ethics: Must handle sensitive data responsibly and comply with data protection laws.
- Reliability: Systems must be robust and reliable in challenging environments.

Potential AI Use Cases for Human Resources and Capacity Building

Managing human resources effectively is essential for NRC to optimize its operations and impact. AI technologies can assist in talent management, staff development, and capacity building by automating processes and providing personalized experiences. The use cases can be divided into Direct Prompting Use Cases and Integrated or Customized Use Cases.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Human Resources and Capacity Building

- **Drafting Job Descriptions and Communications:**
 - AI can help create initial drafts of job postings, emails, and HR policies.

- *Example:* An HR officer uses ChatGPT to draft a job description for a new role, which is then reviewed and customized.
- **Interview Question Generation:**
 - Generating lists of interview questions tailored to specific roles or competencies.
 - *Example:* Creating a set of behavioral interview questions for a project manager position.
- **Answering HR Policy Queries:**
 - Providing quick summaries or explanations of HR policies and procedures.
 - *Example:* An employee asks AI about the organization's leave policy and receives a summarized response.
- **Personal Development Suggestions:**
 - Offering general advice on skill development or career progression.
 - *Example:* An employee seeks recommendations on improving leadership skills and receives suggestions for activities or resources.

Benefits:

- Efficiency: Saves time on drafting and responding to common queries.
- Consistency: Helps maintain uniformity in communications and documentation.
- Accessibility: Provides immediate assistance to staff.

Considerations:

- Policy Accuracy: Ensure AI-generated content aligns with NRC's official policies.
- Confidentiality: Avoid sharing sensitive employee information with external AI tools.
- Human Oversight: Review AI outputs for compliance and appropriateness.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Human Resources and Capacity Building

- **AI-Powered Skills Assessment and Matching:**
 - Utilizing AI to analyze employee skills, performance data, and role requirements to match staff with suitable positions and training opportunities.
 - *Example:* An AI system reviews staff profiles to recommend internal candidates for a new project based on required competencies.
- **Personalized Learning and Development Platforms:**
 - Developing adaptive learning systems that provide customized training content based on individual learning needs and preferences.
 - *Example:* An AI platform curates a personalized learning path for an employee, adjusting content based on progress and feedback.
- **Talent Gap Analysis:**
 - Analyzing organizational skills gaps and predicting future HR needs.
 - *Example:* AI identifies a shortage of staff with expertise in a specific area, informing recruitment and training strategies.
- **Employee Engagement and Retention Tools:**
 - Monitoring employee satisfaction and engagement levels through sentiment analysis of feedback and communications.
 - *Example:* An AI tool analyzes survey responses to detect areas of concern, enabling HR to address issues proactively.

- **Automated Onboarding Processes:**

- Streamlining onboarding by automating documentation, training schedules, and orientation materials.
- *Example:* New hires receive an AI-guided onboarding experience tailored to their role and location.

Benefits:

- **Enhanced Efficiency:** Automates time-consuming HR tasks.
- **Improved Staff Development:** Provides targeted training and career development opportunities.
- **Data-Driven Decisions:** Informs HR strategies with actionable insights.
- **Personalization:** Enhances employee experience through tailored interactions.

Considerations:

- **Data Privacy and Compliance:** Must protect employee data and comply with privacy regulations.
- **Technical Resources:** Requires investment in HR technology and expertise.
- **Change Management:** Staff may need support adapting to new systems.
- **Ethical Use:** Ensure AI applications promote fairness and do not introduce bias.

Potential AI Use Cases for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning

Effective monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) are essential for the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) to assess program performance, understand impact, and inform strategic decisions. Analyzing large volumes of data from diverse sources can be time-consuming and error-prone, hindering timely decision-making and program adaptation. AI technologies offer significant potential to enhance these processes. AI use cases in this domain can be categorized into Direct Prompting Use Cases and Integrated or Customized Use Cases.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning

- **Data Summarization and Report Generation:**

- AI can help summarize field reports, beneficiary feedback, and program data into concise reports or presentations.
- *Example:* Using ChatGPT to generate a summary of weekly field reports highlighting key achievements and challenges.

- **Insights Generation:**

- AI models can assist in interpreting data by providing insights or suggesting trends based on the provided information.
- *Example:* Asking an AI model to identify common themes from a set of beneficiary feedback comments.

- **Question Answering:**

- Quickly obtaining answers to specific questions about MEL practices, methodologies, or data interpretation.
- *Example:* Inquiring about best practices for conducting impact evaluations in conflict zones.

Benefits:

- **Time Efficiency:** Reduces the time spent on manual data analysis and report writing.

- **Accessibility:** Makes analytical support available to staff without specialized training.
- **Enhanced Understanding:** Helps in making sense of complex data through simplified explanations.

Considerations:

- **Data Privacy:** Ensure no sensitive or confidential data is input into AI tools that process data externally.
- **Accuracy Verification:** AI-generated insights should be verified for accuracy and relevance.
- **Contextualization:** AI models may not fully capture the nuances of the humanitarian context without proper guidance.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning

- **Automated Data Analysis:**
 - Implement AI-powered tools that process large volumes of structured and unstructured data, identifying trends, patterns, and anomalies.
 - *Example:* An AI system that analyzes beneficiary feedback, survey results, and field reports to generate real-time dashboards displaying key performance indicators.
- **Natural Language Processing for Qualitative Data:**
 - Utilizing NLP to analyze text data, such as open-ended survey responses or interview transcripts, extracting themes and sentiments.
 - *Example:* An AI tool that categorizes beneficiary comments into thematic areas, highlighting prevalent concerns or positive feedback.
- **Predictive Analytics:**
 - Developing machine learning models that predict program outcomes or identify factors contributing to success or challenges.
 - *Example:* Predicting which programs are likely to meet their targets based on historical data and current trends.
- **Anomaly Detection:**
 - Identifying irregularities in data that may indicate errors, fraud, or unexpected events requiring attention.
 - *Example:* Detecting sudden drops in service utilization that could signal access issues or security concerns.
- **Automated Reporting Systems:**
 - Creating systems that automatically generate comprehensive MEL reports, integrating data from multiple sources and formatting them according to NRC standards.
 - *Example:* A system that compiles monthly MEL reports with visuals and narratives, ready for review and dissemination.

Benefits:

- **Efficiency and Timeliness:** Accelerates data processing and reporting cycles.
- **Improved Accuracy:** Reduces human errors in data analysis.
- **Enhanced Insights:** Uncovers deeper trends and patterns not easily detected manually.

- Resource Optimization: Allows MEL staff to focus on strategic analysis rather than routine data processing.

Considerations:

- Technical Infrastructure: Requires investment in data management systems and AI technologies.
- Data Quality: AI models depend on high-quality data; data cleansing processes may be necessary.
- Staff Training: Personnel need training to understand and interpret AI-generated outputs.
- Ethical Use: Ensure compliance with data protection policies and ethical guidelines when handling sensitive information.

Potential AI Use Cases for Proposal Development and Reporting

Proposal development and reporting are critical for securing funding and maintaining accountability to donors. NRC faces challenges due to manual, time-consuming tasks that divert resources from strategic activities. AI technologies can streamline these processes, improving efficiency and the quality of outputs.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Proposal Development and Reporting

- **Drafting Proposal Sections:**
 - AI can generate initial drafts of proposal components based on prompts outlining required content.
 - *Example:* Using ChatGPT to draft a needs assessment section for a proposal, based on provided key points.
- **Editing and Proofreading:**
 - AI models can assist in refining language, checking grammar, and improving the clarity of documents.
 - *Example:* Asking an AI model to proofread a draft report and suggest improvements for readability.
- **Formatting Assistance:**
 - Providing guidance on structuring documents according to donor guidelines.
 - *Example:* Inquiring about the typical structure for a proposal to a specific donor.
- **Compliance Checks:**
 - Getting quick summaries of donor requirements or best practices.
 - *Example:* Asking for a checklist of mandatory components for a proposal submission to a particular funding agency.

Benefits:

- Time Savings: Speeds up the drafting and editing process.
- Improved Quality: Enhances the professionalism and compliance of documents.
- Accessibility: Supports staff regardless of their experience level with specific donors.

Considerations:

- Confidentiality: Avoid sharing sensitive proposal details with external AI services.
- Accuracy: AI-generated content should be carefully reviewed for alignment with NRC's standards and donor requirements.

- Customization: AI outputs may require significant tailoring to fit the specific context and needs.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Proposal Development and Reporting

- **Robotic Process Automation (RPA):**
 - Automating routine tasks such as data entry, document formatting, and compilation of standard sections.
 - *Example:* An RPA tool that fills in standard organizational information in proposal templates.
- **AI-Powered Compliance Checking:**
 - Using AI to automatically review proposals and reports for compliance with donor requirements, highlighting areas needing adjustment.
 - *Example:* An AI system scans a draft proposal to ensure all donor-specific guidelines are met and flags any omissions.
- **Analysis of Historical Data:**
 - Leveraging AI to analyze past proposals, funding trends, and donor feedback to inform the development of new proposals.
 - *Example:* An AI model identifies successful strategies from previous proposals and suggests incorporating similar elements.
- **Content Management Integration:**
 - Integrating AI into content repositories to suggest relevant content for proposals based on keywords or topics.
 - *Example:* When drafting a proposal on education programs, the system recommends previously used language or statistics.
- **Financial Data Automation:**
 - Automating the preparation and verification of budget tables and financial reports.
 - *Example:* An AI tool that populates budget templates and checks for consistency with narrative sections.

Benefits:

- Efficiency: Reduces time spent on administrative tasks, allowing staff to focus on strategic proposal development.
- Enhanced Quality: Improves the consistency and compliance of submissions.
- Data-Driven Insights: Provides valuable information to strengthen proposals and align them with donor priorities.
- Increased Competitiveness: Enhances the likelihood of securing funding by improving proposal quality.

Considerations:

- Integration Effort: Requires technical integration with existing systems and databases.
- Data Security: Must ensure that sensitive financial and organizational data are protected.
- Staff Adaptation: Change management and training are necessary to ensure staff adopt new tools effectively.

- **Cost-Benefit Analysis:** Evaluate the investment required against the expected gains in efficiency and funding success.

Potential AI Use Cases for Technical Program Design and Implementation

Effective technical program design and implementation are crucial for the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) to address the complex humanitarian needs in conflict-affected regions like Ukraine. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies can offer significant enhancements in identifying priority needs, optimizing resource allocation, and improving overall program effectiveness. However, it is imperative to approach these applications with substantial caution, particularly regarding data privacy and the handling of personally identifiable data (PID). Any sharing or processing of PID would require a comprehensive Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and informed consent from beneficiaries, aligning with NRC's commitment to ethical standards and legal compliance.

Direct Prompting Use Cases for Technical Program Design and Implementation

- **Research and Information Gathering:**
 - AI can assist in summarizing public reports, academic papers, and open-source data to inform program strategies.
 - *Example:* A program manager uses ChatGPT to summarize recent studies on displacement trends in Ukraine to identify emerging needs.
- **Idea Generation and Brainstorming:**
 - Generating innovative approaches to program challenges by soliciting ideas from AI models.
 - *Example:* Seeking suggestions for livelihood programs that have been effective in similar contexts globally.
- **Best Practices and Lessons Learned:**
 - Obtaining insights on successful interventions and methodologies used by other organizations.
 - *Example:* Asking for examples of effective shelter solutions in post-conflict environments.

Benefits:

- **Immediate Access:** Quick retrieval of information without the need for technical setup.
- **Time Efficiency:** Saves time in researching and compiling information.
- **Cost-Effective:** No additional investment in technology infrastructure is required.

Considerations:

- **Data Privacy:** Ensure no sensitive or personally identifiable information is input into AI tools.
- **Verification Needed:** AI-generated content should be cross-checked with reliable sources for accuracy.
- **Contextual Limitations:** AI models may lack specific local context or the most recent data.

Integrated or Customized Use Cases for Technical Program Design and Implementation

- **AI-Powered Needs Assessment Tools:**
 - Developing machine learning models to analyze data from surveys, satellite imagery, social media, and other datasets to identify priority needs and vulnerabilities.
 - *Example:* An AI system processes satellite imagery to detect damaged infrastructure, indicating areas requiring immediate intervention.
- **Resource Allocation and Logistics Optimization:**
 - Using AI algorithms for supply chain management, optimizing resource utilization, and streamlining logistics.
 - *Example:* An AI tool calculates the most efficient routes for aid delivery, considering factors like road conditions and security risks.
- **Predictive Analytics for Program Planning:**
 - Employing AI to forecast future humanitarian needs based on historical data and emerging trends.
 - *Example:* Predictive models estimate population movements to anticipate and prepare for increased demand in certain regions.
- **AI-Powered Cash Assistance Decision Support:**
 - Developing an AI-driven system to assist in determining the most appropriate modality for cash assistance (cash, voucher, or in-kind) based on contextual factors.
 - *Example:* An AI tool analyzes responses to an assessment questionnaire, calculates scores for each modality, and generates real-time recommendations with explanations, integrated with existing data management systems.

Benefits:

- **Enhanced Effectiveness:** Data-driven insights lead to more targeted and impactful interventions.
- **Operational Efficiency:** Optimizes resources and reduces waste.
- **Proactive Response:** Anticipates needs, allowing for timely action.

Considerations:

- **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA):** Any use of personally identifiable data requires a DPIA to identify and mitigate risks associated with data processing.
- **Informed Consent:**
- **Clear communication with beneficiaries** is essential to obtain informed consent for data use, explaining how their information will contribute to program effectiveness.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Compliance with data protection laws, such as GDPR, is mandatory. This includes secure data storage, processing protocols, and breach notification procedures.
- **Ethical Use:** Adherence to ethical standards in data handling to maintain trust and protect the rights of beneficiaries.

- **Complex Implementation:** Technical integration requires expertise, resources, and time, making it a less immediate solution compared to direct prompting use cases.

Cautionary Notes:

- **Not a Low-Hanging Fruit:**
 - Due to the complexities of data protection and the need for informed consent, these applications are not the easiest to implement and should not be considered quick wins.
- **Risk of Data Misuse:**
 - Mishandling sensitive data can lead to breaches of privacy, legal consequences, and damage to NRC's reputation.
- **Resource Intensive:**
 - Significant investment in technology infrastructure and staff training is required.
- **Alignment with NRC's Principles:**
 - **Equity and Inclusion:** By carefully implementing AI tools, NRC can ensure resources reach the most vulnerable populations.
 - **Accountability:** Thorough assessments and transparent communication uphold accountability to beneficiaries and stakeholders.
 - **Ethical Conduct:** Prioritizing data protection and informed consent aligns with NRC's commitment to ethical humanitarian action.

While AI technologies present promising opportunities to enhance technical program design, implementation, and cash assistance programs, they require careful and cautious adoption. Any processing of personally identifiable data mandates thorough Data Protection Impact Assessments and robust beneficiary communication to obtain informed consent. These use cases involve significant complexity and risk, making them less suitable as immediate, low-hanging fruit. NRC should prioritize data privacy, ethical considerations, and regulatory compliance in all AI initiatives. By proceeding cautiously and responsibly, NRC can leverage AI's potential to improve humanitarian outcomes while upholding the rights and trust of the communities it serves.

Cross-Cutting Risks with AI NLP for NRC Ukraine

While AI NLP technologies present significant opportunities for enhancing NRC Ukraine's humanitarian operations, their responsible adoption and implementation require a comprehensive understanding and mitigation of potential risks. From data privacy concerns to algorithmic biases and security vulnerabilities, these cutting-edge technologies can pose challenges that must be proactively addressed. This section explores the cross-cutting risks associated with leveraging AI NLP in NRC Ukraine's humanitarian efforts, highlighting the need for robust governance frameworks, ethical safeguards, and a commitment to upholding core humanitarian principles. By identifying and mitigating these risks, NRC Ukraine can harness the transformative potential of AI while ensuring responsible and trustworthy deployment.

Data Privacy and Protection Concerns

As NRC Ukraine integrates AI NLP technologies, data privacy and protection concerns must be carefully addressed. There is a risk of data breaches or misuse of sensitive beneficiary information, which could undermine trust and compromise the safety of vulnerable populations. Ensuring data privacy and security is particularly challenging in conflict zones, where cyber threats and infrastructure limitations may heighten vulnerabilities. NRC must implement robust data governance measures, secure infrastructure, and stringent protocols to mitigate these risks and safeguard the confidentiality and integrity of beneficiary data, particularly in sensitive humanitarian contexts. To address these concerns, NRC Ukraine should consider adopting robust data governance frameworks and ethical principles aligned with industry standards, such as Microsoft's Responsible AI Standards, as recommended by Kazaz (2023).²

Algorithmic Bias and Ethical Implications

AI models can perpetuate biases present in their training data or reflect the biases of their developers, posing significant ethical implications. In humanitarian contexts, algorithmic biases could lead to unintended discrimination or unfair treatment of certain groups, exacerbating existing inequalities and compromising core principles of equity and inclusion. As highlighted by Sandvik, Lidén, and Jumbert (2023),³ while AI can perform tasks more efficiently and cost-effectively than humans, it can also fail in ways that humans never can. This underscores the importance of addressing potential biases and ethical implications associated with AI adoption in humanitarian contexts. NRC Ukraine must prioritize ethical AI development by identifying and mitigating biases, ensuring diverse and representative data, and implementing rigorous testing and auditing procedures. Failure to address algorithmic biases could undermine the credibility and effectiveness of NRC's humanitarian efforts and erode public trust.

Overreliance on AI and Erosion of Human Expertise

While AI NLP offers valuable capabilities, there is a risk of overreliance on its recommendations, potentially devaluing human expertise and contextual understanding. If not managed properly, AI-driven decision-making could lead to an erosion of the nuanced, human-centric approach that is crucial in humanitarian contexts. NRC Ukraine must ensure that AI systems complement and enhance, rather than replace, human decision-making processes. Maintaining a balance and fostering a culture of human oversight, critical thinking, and ethical deliberation is essential to prevent over-automation and preserve the invaluable expertise of humanitarian professionals on the ground.

² Kazaz, J. (2023). The Impact of AI on the Society: Key Takeaways. GLOBSEC Event Centre for Democracy & Resilience, August 7. Retrieved from <https://www.globsec.org/what-we-do/events/impact-ai-society-key-takeaways> [Accessed April 20, 2024].

³Sandvik, B., Lidén, K., & Jumbert, M. G. (2023). Artificial intelligence could be a game-changer for the humanitarian sector. Panorama News, October 13, 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.panoramanyheter.no/bistandsbransjen-humanitaer-bistand-kunstig-intelligens/kunstig-intelligens-kan-bli-en-gamechanger-for-humanitaer-sektor/347728> [Accessed April 20, 2024].

Lack of Transparency and Accountability

Many AI systems, especially complex deep learning models used for NLP tasks, can be opaque and difficult to interpret, posing challenges for transparency and accountability. In high-stakes humanitarian decision-making, a lack of transparency and explainability can undermine trust, scrutiny, and the ability to justify decisions that significantly impact vulnerable populations. NRC Ukraine must prioritize the development and deployment of explainable AI systems that provide clear rationales and audit trails, enabling transparency and accountability in decision-making processes. Failure to address this risk could compromise NRC's credibility and adherence to core humanitarian principles.

The use of AI-generated images in humanitarian communication and documentation efforts presents additional transparency and accountability challenges. As highlighted by Jumbert (2024),⁴ the intentional or unintentional use of AI-generated images to illustrate real events or suffering can contribute to a blurring of lines between reality and fabrication, potentially undermining public trust, and credibility. While such images may aim to engage audiences without exposing real individuals, they risk failing to serve the core purposes of documenting and bearing witness to humanitarian crises. NRC Ukraine must exercise caution and establish clear guidelines for the responsible use of AI-generated visuals, ensuring transparency about their nature and limitations, and prioritizing the use of authentic documentation whenever possible.

Security Vulnerabilities and Misuse Potential

The rapid development of generative AI applications poses unique security risks. As highlighted by Silverman (2023)⁵, the pace of AI deployment often outpaces traditional software development processes, leading to potential vulnerabilities and lack of oversight. Moreover, malicious actors may exploit AI tools to create sophisticated malware, phishing attacks, and deepfakes, compromising cybersecurity and data integrity. NRC Ukraine must remain vigilant against these emerging threats by implementing robust cybersecurity measures, regular security audits, and strict access controls to mitigate the risks associated with AI adoption in humanitarian contexts.

Operational and Environmental Challenges

The operational environment in conflict zones and humanitarian settings can pose significant challenges for the effective implementation and maintenance of AI NLP systems. Issues such as power outages, limited internet connectivity, and infrastructure constraints can disrupt the functionality and reliability of these technologies. Additionally, cybersecurity threats, including malware and cyber-attacks, can compromise the security and integrity of AI systems, potentially leading to data breaches or system failures. NRC Ukraine must carefully assess the operational environment, develop contingency plans, and implement resilient

⁴ Jumbert, M. G. (2024). The AI Dilemma: Can Artificial Images of War and Suffering Stir Empathy? *Global Policy Opinion*, March 15, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.globalpolicyjournal.com/blog/15/03/2024/ai-dilemma-can-artificial-images-war-and-suffering-stir-empathy> [Accessed April 20, 2024].

⁵ Silverman, E. (2023). 5 security risks of generative AI and how to prepare for them. *Zapier Blog*, June 14, 2023. Retrieved from <https://zapier.com/blog/ai-security-risks/> [Accessed April 20, 2024].

solutions to ensure the continuous and secure operation of AI NLP systems in challenging humanitarian contexts.

Regulatory and Legal Implications

As AI technologies continue to evolve, regulatory frameworks surrounding data privacy, AI ethics, and responsible use are also rapidly evolving. NRC Ukraine must stay informed about the latest regulations and legal requirements related to the deployment and application of AI NLP systems in humanitarian contexts. Failure to comply with these regulations could result in legal risks, financial penalties, or reputational damage. Additionally, there may be potential legal liabilities associated with AI decision-making, particularly in high-stakes scenarios where decisions could significantly impact vulnerable populations. Proactive engagement with legal experts and compliance with relevant regulations is crucial.

Implementation Considerations

Following the presentation of sector-specific AI applications, this report delves into implementation considerations. Factors such as existing IT infrastructure, staff training needs, data privacy concerns, operational challenges, and change management strategies are vital for successful integration. Addressing these facets ensures a seamless transition and maximizes the benefits of AI solutions, especially in complex environments like conflict zones.

Existing IT Infrastructure and Data Management Capabilities

In planning the integration of AI solutions into NRC Ukraine's operations, meticulous attention to various factors is essential to facilitate successful adoption and mitigate potential challenges. This segment delves into crucial considerations for implementing AI technologies within the specific operational framework of NRC Ukraine's humanitarian endeavours. An appraisal of NRC Ukraine's current IT infrastructure, encompassing hardware, software, and network capacities, is imperative to gauge its readiness in supporting AI implementations. Concurrently, an evaluation of the organization's data management practices, spanning data collection, storage, security, and governance, is vital to ascertain the availability and quality of requisite data for AI systems.

Identification of any gaps or constraints within the existing infrastructure and data management capabilities is imperative prior to the implementation of AI solutions. Moreover, considerations regarding the scalability and interoperability of AI systems with NRC Ukraine's extant technology stack are pivotal to ensure seamless integration and enduring sustainability. By meticulously assessing these facets, NRC Ukraine can lay a robust foundation for the effective incorporation of AI technologies into its operational framework.

Staff Training and Capacity Building

In considering the integration of AI solutions within NRC Ukraine's operations, addressing staff training and capacity building is paramount to ensure successful implementation and utilization of these technologies. This section outlines the essential steps required to bolster staff competency and readiness in engaging with AI-powered tools and methodologies.

Firstly, a thorough assessment of the current level of AI literacy and technical proficiency among NRC Ukraine's staff is necessary to pinpoint specific training and capacity-building needs. Subsequently, tailored training programs should be developed to equip personnel with the requisite knowledge and skills to effectively utilize and interpret outputs generated by AI-powered tools. Furthermore, as suggested by Kazaz (2023), NRC Ukraine could consider integrating AI-relevant subjects, such as data science, into its staff training programs to equip personnel with the necessary skills for effective AI adoption.⁶

Additionally, comprehensive training initiatives should encompass areas such as data literacy, AI ethics, and responsible AI practices. This multifaceted approach ensures that staff are adept at making informed decisions and adeptly navigating the ethical considerations inherent in AI deployments, thereby mitigating potential risks. Furthermore, fostering a culture of continuous learning and knowledge sharing is imperative to keep staff abreast of the latest advancements in AI technologies and their evolving applications within humanitarian contexts. By encouraging ongoing professional development and facilitating avenues for collaboration and exchange of insights, NRC Ukraine can cultivate a workforce that is not only proficient in leveraging AI solutions but also adaptive and innovative in addressing emerging challenges.

Data Privacy and Ethical Concerns

In addressing the integration of AI solutions within NRC Ukraine's operations, careful attention to data privacy and ethical considerations is paramount to uphold the organization's commitment to safeguarding beneficiary information and adhering to ethical standards. This section outlines key measures to ensure the responsible and ethical use of AI technologies while prioritizing data protection.

As noted by Silverman (2023), the use of generative AI tools poses a risk of inadvertently exposing confidential or sensitive data, including beneficiary information, intellectual property, and strategic information. NRC Ukraine must establish clear protocols and train staff on the appropriate use of AI tools, ensuring that sensitive data is not shared or fed into these systems.

Additionally, conducting thorough data privacy impact assessments is essential to identify and mitigate potential risks associated with the processing of personal data, particularly if it involves information from beneficiaries. Clear guidelines and policies should be developed to govern the ethical use of AI, addressing issues such as algorithmic bias, transparency, accountability, and human rights considerations. These guidelines should serve as a framework to ensure that AI systems are deployed in a manner that upholds ethical standards and respects the rights and dignity of all individuals involved.

Furthermore, engagement with affected communities, partners, and stakeholders is vital to foster a participatory approach to the development and deployment of AI solutions. By soliciting input and feedback from diverse stakeholders, including beneficiaries, NRC Ukraine

⁶ Kazaz, J. (2023)

can ensure that AI initiatives are responsive to the needs, concerns, and cultural contexts of those they aim to serve. In conclusion, a comprehensive approach that integrates robust data privacy protocols, ethical guidelines, and stakeholder engagement is essential to ensure the responsible and inclusive use of AI technologies within NRC Ukraine's humanitarian operations.

Operational Environment Challenges

In navigating the integration of AI solutions within NRC Ukraine's operations, it's crucial to recognize and address the unique challenges posed by the operational environment, particularly in conflict-affected areas. This section delineates key strategies to surmount operational hurdles and ensure the effective deployment of AI technologies amidst adversity. Foremost, it is imperative to consider the distinct challenges prevalent in conflict-affected regions of Ukraine, such as infrastructure damage, connectivity issues, and security risks. Understanding these dynamics is essential for devising tailored approaches to AI implementation that account for the operational realities on the ground.

Concurrently, assessing the reliability and availability of critical resources—such as power supply and internet connectivity—is vital for the seamless functioning of AI systems in the field. Developing contingency plans and backup mechanisms is imperative to mitigate potential disruptions or instability that may arise due to infrastructure limitations or security concerns. Furthermore, evaluating the potential impact of the operational environment on data collection, transmission, and storage is paramount. Implementing robust measures to uphold data integrity and security safeguards against risks associated with operating in volatile contexts, ensuring that sensitive information remains protected and uncompromised.

In essence, by proactively addressing operational challenges and implementing appropriate mitigation strategies, NRC Ukraine can bolster the resilience of its AI-powered operations in conflict-affected areas. This approach ensures continuity and effectiveness in delivering humanitarian assistance while navigating the complexities of the operational landscape.

Feasibility of Implementing AI Solutions in NRC Ukraine's Context

In conclusion, the feasibility of integrating AI solutions into NRC Ukraine's operations hinges on a range of factors, including organizational readiness, resource availability, and the specific use cases under consideration. While the potential benefits of AI in augmenting efficiency, decision-making, and impact are considerable, several challenges must be addressed to ensure successful implementation.

NRC Ukraine's existing IT infrastructure and data management capabilities are pivotal in determining the feasibility of AI adoption. A comprehensive assessment of these systems, coupled with necessary upgrades and enhancements, is essential for the seamless integration of AI technologies. Moreover, the organization must prioritize investing in staff training and capacity building to foster the requisite AI literacy and technical skills. This investment ensures that personnel can proficiently leverage AI tools and interpret their outputs effectively.

Addressing data privacy and ethical concerns is paramount to instilling trust in AI solutions. Robust data governance frameworks and engagement with stakeholders are crucial elements in safeguarding sensitive information and mitigating risks associated with AI implementation. The unique challenges posed by the operational environment in conflict-affected areas necessitate adaptable and resilient solutions. Infrastructure damage, connectivity issues, and security risks must be carefully navigated to ensure the reliability and effectiveness of AI systems in the field.

Furthermore, effective change management and adoption strategies are critical for successful AI implementation. A comprehensive plan, coupled with a phased approach and stakeholder engagement, facilitates the transition to AI-powered workflows and fosters trust among all involved parties. In sum, while challenges exist, the feasibility of implementing AI solutions in NRC Ukraine's operations is achievable through strategic planning, investment, and a commitment to responsible practices. By harnessing the potential of AI technologies, NRC Ukraine can enhance its humanitarian efforts in conflict-affected regions, ultimately improving outcomes for those it serves.

Recommendations for Responsible AI Implementation at NRC Ukraine

Considering the evolving landscape of humanitarian aid, NRC Ukraine is advised to strategically integrate AI solutions within its operations. The following comprehensive recommendations are designed to guide the organization's approach to AI implementation and continuous monitoring. Emphasizing a measured, incremental approach that recognizes existing staff usage of AI and prepares for increased future utilization, these recommendations ensure alignment with humanitarian principles and organizational objectives, fostering trust and upholding the transparency of AI systems.

Prioritize Practical AI Tools

NRC Ukraine should begin by identifying AI-powered tools that offer immediate efficiency gains and assess their feasibility within existing workflows. These tools may include speech recognition, translation software, and automation of repetitive tasks. The organization should prioritize tools that can be seamlessly integrated into current processes and require minimal disruption to staff routines. Implementing these tools gradually, while providing necessary training and support, will ensure a smooth transition and maximize adoption.

Automate Basic Processes

Conduct a thorough review of operations to identify repetitive, time-consuming tasks suitable for automation. This may include data entry, report generation, and basic data analysis. By evaluating the potential time and resource savings associated with automating these processes, NRC Ukraine can make informed decisions about where to invest in automation solutions. Implementing these solutions incrementally, while ensuring staff are adequately trained and supported throughout the process, will help mitigate any potential resistance to change and ensure a successful transition.

Establish Ethical Guidelines and Governance Structures

Develop comprehensive principles and guidelines to ensure the ethical and responsible use of AI. These guidelines should emphasize transparency, accountability, and the importance of human judgment in decision-making processes. They should address issues related to data privacy, security, and bias, ensuring that AI systems are fair, unbiased, and do not perpetuate or amplify existing inequalities. Regular reviews and updates of these guidelines will reflect evolving best practices and lessons learned from the organization's AI implementation experiences.

Prioritize Rights-Based Approaches and Algorithmic Accountability

Integrate rights-based approaches into the AI strategy, emphasizing collective rights and algorithmic accountability. This involves developing mechanisms to ensure that AI systems respect and uphold the rights of affected communities, including access to information, security, and welfare. Establishing processes for transparent and explainable AI decision-making promotes accountability and enables affected populations to understand and scrutinize algorithms that impact their lives. By centering rights-based approaches and algorithmic accountability, NRC Ukraine can foster trust, inclusivity, and ethical AI adoption aligned with its humanitarian mission.

Foster Organizational Intelligence and Capacity Building

Encourage knowledge-sharing among staff and invest in training programs that enhance data literacy, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. By fostering a culture of continuous learning and promoting a data-driven approach to decision-making and program design, the organization can build the necessary capacity to effectively harness the benefits of AI. This ensures that staff are equipped to identify potential risks and challenges associated with AI adoption and can contribute to the development of mitigation strategies.

Adopt an Incremental Implementation Approach

Start with simple, low-risk AI applications and gradually expand to more complex use cases as readiness and capacity grow. By continuously monitoring and evaluating the impact of AI solutions, NRC Ukraine can make informed decisions about where to invest further resources and how to optimize existing tools. This approach allows the organization to identify and address any unintended consequences or challenges that may arise during the implementation process.

Engage Stakeholders and Foster Collaboration

Actively engage with beneficiaries, partners, and other stakeholders to maximize the benefits of AI for humanitarian action. Collaboration and partnerships are key to exchanging knowledge, sharing lessons learned, and co-creating solutions that address common challenges. By involving affected communities in the design of AI tools, NRC Ukraine ensures cultural sensitivity and relevance. Working together with other humanitarian organizations, academia, and the private sector promotes shared standards and responsible AI use in crisis contexts.

Establish Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms

Implement robust monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the impact of AI initiatives and inform ongoing strategy. This involves defining key performance indicators (KPIs) for AI implementations, regularly reviewing AI performance and ethical compliance, and adjusting strategies based on performance data and feedback. Continuous assessment ensures alignment with organizational goals and the ability to make data-driven decisions.

Conclusion

The rapid advancement of AI and NLP technologies offers significant opportunities for NRC Ukraine to enhance its humanitarian operations, increase efficiency, and improve decision-making capabilities. By integrating AI into various aspects of its work—such as data analysis, needs assessments, beneficiary communication, and program design—the organization can streamline processes, automate repetitive tasks, and extract valuable insights from large volumes of data. This integration will enable more effective and timely humanitarian interventions, ultimately better serving crisis-affected communities.

However, realizing the full potential of AI requires careful navigation of ethical, operational, and strategic challenges. NRC Ukraine must approach AI implementation with a strong commitment to responsible adoption and governance, ensuring that the use of these technologies aligns with humanitarian principles and does not compromise the privacy, security, or dignity of affected populations. This necessitates the development of robust data protection protocols, ethical guidelines, and accountability mechanisms. Ongoing engagement with staff, beneficiaries, and external stakeholders is essential to foster trust and transparency throughout the AI implementation process.

Building the necessary technical capacity is also critical for successful integration. This involves investing in staff training and development, fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation, and adapting processes and workflows to accommodate new technologies. Establishing cross-functional collaboration and promoting knowledge-sharing will enhance the organization's ability to adapt to the rapidly evolving landscape of AI technologies, staying abreast of emerging trends, best practices, and potential risks.

Collaboration and partnerships will be key to maximizing the benefits of AI for humanitarian action. As suggested by Sandvik, Lidén, and Jumbert (2023), development aid agencies, the voluntary sector, and individual employees should be actively involved in discussions on the consequences of generative AI for humanitarian work. NRC Ukraine should engage with other humanitarian organizations, academia, the private sector, and affected communities to exchange knowledge, share lessons learned, and co-create solutions that address common challenges. By working together, the humanitarian sector can develop shared standards, tools, and approaches that promote the responsible and effective use of AI in crisis contexts.

Looking ahead, AI holds immense potential to transform humanitarian action. As technology continues to advance, it will open new possibilities for anticipating and responding to crises, delivering aid more efficiently, and empowering affected populations to play a greater role in shaping decisions that affect their lives. Realizing this potential will require concerted efforts

from humanitarian organizations, donors, policymakers, and technology providers to prioritize responsible AI adoption, invest in capacity building and infrastructure, and foster a culture of innovation and adaptation.

NRC Ukraine has an opportunity to be at the forefront of this transformation. By leveraging its expertise, networks, and resources to pioneer new approaches to humanitarian action that harness the power of AI, the organization can uphold the highest standards of ethics, accountability, and human rights. By embracing this opportunity and committing to responsible AI adoption, NRC Ukraine can enhance its operations and contribute to the wider effort to create a more effective, efficient, and equitable humanitarian system that places the needs and rights of crisis-affected populations at its heart.

In conclusion, while the journey toward AI integration may be complex and challenging, the rewards—in terms of improved outcomes for affected populations and a more effective humanitarian system—are well worth the effort. By approaching this opportunity with a spirit of continuous learning, collaboration, and adaptability, and by prioritizing responsible adoption and governance, NRC Ukraine can position itself as a leader in the humanitarian sector's efforts to harness the transformative potential of AI for good.

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